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Considerations and Logistics For Global Ground and in-Flight Trace Contaminant Testing

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Abstract

Purpose: Aircraft ground and flight testing have constraints that must be considered before and during testing to ensure safety of the aircraft operator and test crew.

Methodology: Dr. Richard Fox shares from his 35 years of aircraft cabin air quality planning and testing experiences.

Findings: The industry knew very little about sources of bleed air odors in the first days of testing. Factors such as microbial growth and humidity were first considered as sources for dirty sock odors from aircraft environmental control systems. Little was known during first test encounters as to which equipment would be most appropriate for testing. Much has been learned and test equipment has evolved to current day methods which can speciate chemicals to parts per trillion levels, and portable battery powered equipment such as the Airsense Aerotracer that have been developed through collaboration between aircraft maintenance and sensor manufacturers to provide contaminant source identification.

Research Limitations: Sampling and analytical methods for ground and flight testing have environmental and operational constraints. Aircraft bleed systems produce air at high temperature and pressure which must be conditioned before introduction into real time analyzers or for gathering retrospective samples. Data gathered at altitude (low atmospheric pressure) may require correction for comparison to data gathered at baseline conditions (higher pressure). Sampling location considerations are also of importance. The size and weight of the equipment must be considered. Availability of power if required for equipment must be considered and may constrain types of equipment that can be brought on board. Weight and balance issues also must be addressed for flight test planning. Logistics of transporting and uploading equipment to the aircraft also are not trivial. Test planning begins weeks ahead of a test and includes development of a test plan, shipping lists, aircraft sampling locations, identifying and obtaining special power converters and frequency changers, EMI testing of electronic equipment that will be operated during flights, developing a sampling plan, flight test planning, and flight test airworthiness approval.

Practical Implications: Many changes have occurred over the past 35 years in understanding of testing requirements, equipment capability has evolved, and more targeted testing is now possible.

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Social Implications: This presentation summarizes experiences learned through collaborative efforts of airlines, aircraft Original Equipment Manufacturers, engine manufacturers, regulators, flight crew, cabin crew, and many others whose services are necessary to conduct testing.

Value and Originality: The author is not aware of any open source publication that discusses sampling and testing aircraft cabin environment aspects that are covered in this presentation. Research papers containing data often discuss instrument details, but not what it takes to organize and implement a test strategy.

Keywords

bleed air, contaminant, measurement, flight test, ground test
